

St. Dominic College of Asia's Bachelor of Science in Biology Batch 2019: A tracer study

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Abstract

This tracer study identified the employability of BS Biology graduates of Batch 2019 at St. Dominic College of Asia. It aimed to determine the postgraduate activities undertaken by the BS Biology graduates after graduation and their current employment status. Using a descriptive research design, six BS Biology alumni members were given a consent to participate in the research, but only five took part in the tracer study. A Google form questionnaire was devised to gather the necessary information from the graduates. The study found that the graduates of the institution possessed the skills and competencies necessary to land a job in this very competitive working arena. It is also revealed that BS Biology graduates have multiple options after their graduation, if they can either proceed to medical school or get a postgraduate degree aligned to their field of specialization. The school-related issues that affect the employment of biology alumni must also be studied by future researchers.

Keywords: *BS Biology, graduates, tracer study, employability.*

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Introduction

Bachelor of Science in Biology is a four-year degree program that deals with the study of living things. The very broad field of Biology includes the understanding of various concepts like anatomy and physiology of various living things, chemical and molecular interactions within cellular structures, relationships of different interrelated fields like systematics, genetics, and evolution, and a wide array of field work and environmental studies. BS Biology is a pre-medical undergraduate program that serves as a stepping stone for medical school that also provides opportunities to other fields like academe, industry-based laboratories, biology-based government related works, and others.

Facing the global and local competitiveness, educational institutions must create competitive graduates who are employable. One factor determining an academic institution's performance is how employable its alumni are. The standard of learning and facilities offered will assist in making sure the graduates have the knowledge, abilities, and values needed to be successful in their respective industries and will therefore play a significant role in determining the quality of graduates (Celis et al., 2013; Rainie & Anderson, 2017; Sisodia & Agarwal, 2017).

Accordingly, it is crucial for higher education institutions to foster an atmosphere where meaningful learning may occur and to equip their graduates to enter the workforce (Kromydas, 2017; Nielsen et al., 2019 as cited in Gutierrez, 2020). The individuals working in the institution must know the scope and requirements of the existing labor market in order to complete this activity. Institutions may analyze their graduates using a tracer approach to find these (Daquis et al., 2016; Gutierrez, 2020; Valdez, 2012).

It is crucial for the School of Health and Science Professions (SHSP)'s BS Biology program to look into its curriculum to support enhanced learning among BS Biology students and better meet the needs of the local and international labor market. This aligns with the goals and objectives of St. Dominic College of Asia to create locally and globally competent graduates (Gutierrez, 2020). In 2019, SDCA produced their first batch of BS Biology graduates, which includes six students: two males and four females. This tracer study utilized a descriptive research design to determine the following information:

1. postgraduate activities undertaken by the BS Biology graduates after graduation; and
2. current employment status of the BS Biology graduates.

Methodology

This tracer study utilized descriptive research design. Six BS Biology Alumni who were part of the first batch of graduates in 2019 represents the total population of the study, but only five took part in the research. Consent letters were sent to each respondents' email which they agreed to by taking part in the said study. A Google form questionnaire was devised to gather the necessary information from the graduates. The Google form comprised of three parts: respondents' profile, post-graduate plans undertaken after graduation, and current employment status. The information gathered was tallied and coded in preparation for the analysis.

Results and Discussion

Out of the six graduates, only five (two males and three females) provided their answers. The following tables represent the distribution of respondents' information and responses.

Postgraduate activity undertaken by the BS Biology graduates after graduation

Planning after graduation is a decision-making task for all graduates. For BS Biology graduates, it is either going to medical school, or taking a postgraduate degree, or taking other options. Table 1 shows that only one respondent took the National Medical Achievement Test (NMAT) and had a plan to go to medical school.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents in terms of the number of takers in the NMAT

Respondents	f	(%)
Yes	1	20
No	4	80
Total	5	100

In addition, Table 2 shows that most of the graduates (80%) have plans to take post-graduate studies after graduation.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents in terms of their plans to take postgraduate studies

Respondents	f	(%)
Yes	4	80
No	1	20
Total	5	100

Current employment status of the BS Biology graduates

After graduation, BS Biology students engaged in the real world where they looked for jobs and got employed in institutions within the community. Table 3 shows that most respondents are currently employed, while one of them is not employed in an institution, but currently handling their own family business.

Table 3. Distribution of respondents in terms of their current employment status

Respondents	f	(%)
Yes	4	80
No (self-employed)	1	20
Total	5	100

Furthermore, most of the respondents are currently employed in private institutions (Table 4), while one of them is working in a government institution.

Table 4. Distribution of respondents in terms of their nature of employment

Respondents	f	(%)
Government	1	25
Private	3	75
Total	4	100

Most of them either have regular, probationary, or contractual status in the institution where they are currently employed (Table 5).

Table 5. Distribution of respondents in terms of their nature of employment in their respective institutions

Respondents	f	(%)
Regular	2	50
Probationary	1	25
Contractual	1	25
Total	4	100

But based on the relatedness of their course in their current work, data shows (Table 6) that 60% of the respondent's current work is related to their course, while 40% is not related to the course that they finished. Self-employed status is also included in the results.

Table 6. Distribution of respondents in terms of the relatedness of their course on their current work

Respondents	f	(%)
Yes	3	60
No	2	40
Total	5	100

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the study found that the graduates of the institution possessed skills and competencies necessary to land a job in this very competitive working arena. The employment rate of the respondents is considered employable with some considerations to the respondents who run their own family business. This study shows that BS Biology graduates have multiple options after their graduation: they can either proceed to medical school or get a postgraduate degree aligned to their field of specialization.

The results of the research also show that most graduates can land a job which can either be related to their course or not. Student competencies can be further strengthened by exposing students to different field works / settings a biologist can go to before graduation such as research works, laboratory facility handling, and others.

Furthermore, encouraging students to attend related trainings and seminars will further enhance their basic skills and give them ideas about different opportunities that they can pursue after graduation. Implementation of the outcomes-based curriculum must prioritize and emphasize the work competencies and ideals of the Biology students. The higher education institution (HEI) has to continue using networking to connect its alumni with employment prospects. The school-related issues that affect the employment of biology alumni must also be studied by future researchers.

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